

MOTIVATION, SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Motivation, Self-Directed Learning, and Academic Performance among Language Learners

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Abstract

This quantitative study explored the participants' level of language learning motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning toward academic performance in English subjects. This descriptive-correlational research design utilized survey questionnaires to gather the data. Through Systematic Random Sampling using Slovin's formula participants in this study consisted of 143 Grade 10 language learners at Bukidnon National High School, Division of Malaybalay City. The findings revealed that the learners have a high level of English Language Learning Motivation for both intrinsic and extrinsic components and a moderately positive attitude toward language learning. Individuals demonstrate a commendable level of self-confidence in acquiring language skills, possess a moderate level of proficiency in self-directed learning that encompasses the three key components, and exhibit exceptional academic achievements. A notable correlation was observed between the academic performance of the learners and their self-efficacy, self-directed learning in terms of ability, and engagement in external learning activities. Moreover, the variables that can predict learners' academic performance are their proficiency in self-directed English learning and their self-efficacy. The implications may result in developing training plans, seminars, and workshops to meet the needs of English language learners at Bukidnon National High School, Malaybalay City Division. Additional research on the subject can be done with many more participants.

Keywords: *language learning motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, self-directed learning, academic performance*

Introduction

Language, thinking, and learning are all interconnected, and language is the cornerstone of all human relationships. According to the Department of Education (2016), the K–12 English Curriculum, or the Language Arts and Multiliteracies Curriculum (LAMC), was created in response to learners' low National Achievement Test performance across courses. Its ultimate purpose is to build communicatively competent and multiliterate learners capable of competing in today's global economy.

However, the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of Grade 6 NAT scores in 2016–2017 and 2017–2018—39.95 and 37.44, respectively—show that it was well below the Department of Education's planned aim. The recent performance of the Philippines in 2018, according to the most highly regarded global student evaluation, Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), reaffirms the concerning results of the National Achievement Test (NAT). According to the PISA results, the Philippines ranked last among 79 nations in reading comprehension. The National Achievement Test (NAT) results indicate something to ponder. Filipino learners in Grades 6, 10, and 12 take the NAT. For the past three years, learners' NAT performance has gradually declined, placing them at the "low mastery" or "low proficiency" descriptive level (DepEd Region, 2019).

Based on the periodical test Mean Percentage Score (MPS) result for the first quarter of the school year 2022-2023 of Bukidnon National High School, the three sections handled by the researcher of the Enhanced Basic Education Program (EBEP) and one section from the Science, Technology, and Engineering (STE) Program have an average Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of only 55.04, which is very far from the desired aim of the Department of Education, which is 75%. This result was quite alarming, and attention to it is essential. Additionally, in terms of reading, out of 1,544 of the total Grade 10 English learners tested in the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Oral Reading Pre-Test for the school year 2022-2023, 1,184 belong to the frustration and instructional reading levels. The result indicates that 70% or more of the total population of the Grade 10 learners of the different programs, considering the four sections that the researcher handles under the EBEP and STE programs, still need assistance in their reading.

As an English teacher at Bukidnon National High School, the researcher found some phenomena related to motivation and attitude toward the English language as influences on academic performance. Per observation during the first quarter, most learners needed help with their attitude and motivation toward their classes, especially in English. Learners do not participate in class discussions and keep quiet in their seats. Compliance with the tasks and assignments could have been better, and these data unmistakably show that it is necessary to inspire and motivate the learners to accomplish their objectives.

Another phenomenon to consider is that most Grade 10 English learners still need more self-efficacy and the capacity to self-direct their learning after the return of face-to-face instruction. They struggled to learn independently and preferred to learn in groups, as was seen. They need help expressing themselves in English regarding the subjects. For them to fully comprehend the teachings, more details, examples, and connections to personal experiences were required.

Academic performance and achieving satisfactory ratings, particularly on the NAT, MPS, and Phil-IRI, are among the key goals at all school levels, with favorable effects for learners and educational systems. As a result, finding the elements impacting learners' academic achievement has always been one of the researcher's primary priorities and one of the issues the Department of Education encounters.

For this purpose, the researcher concentrated on recognizing the impact and level of motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning towards the English language on learners' academic achievement.

According to Orhan-Ozen (2017), academic performance and motivation have positive links. Additionally, Cirak (2021) emphasized that attitude is the propensity that develops an individual's feelings, ideas, and behaviors toward an object. It also has a positive or negative approach to an object or situation (Ciftçi, 2018). Moreover, Dogan (2015) defined self-efficacy as the belief that one can succeed, particularly in specific circumstances or when performing specific tasks. Thus, as reaffirmed Gby Curry et al. (2017), self-directed language learners are more likely to succeed due to resources, practical strategies, and learning results.

Based on the claims mentioned above, this study aimed to examine the level of motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning among Grade 10 learners in Bukidnon National High for the School Year 2022-2023 in the English language and the influence of their academic performance.

Research Questions

The study examined the level of motivation, attitudes, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning towards the English language on learners' academic performance. Specifically, the study explored answering the following research questions:

1. What is the participants' level of motivation in terms of:
 - 1.1. Intrinsic; and
 - 1.2. extrinsic?
2. What is the participants' level of attitude in terms of:
 - 2.1. affective;
 - 2.2. behavioral; and
 - 2.3. cognitive?
3. What is the participants' level of self-efficacy?
4. What is the participants' level of self-directed learning in terms of:
 - 4.1. outside learning;
 - 4.2. ability; and
 - 4.3. management?
5. What is the participants' level of Academic Performance?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the participants' level of Academic Performance in terms of:
 - 6.1. motivation;
 - 6.2. attitude;
 - 6.3. self-efficacy; and
 - 6.4. self-directed learning towards the English language?
7. Which variables, singly or combined, best predict the learners' academic performance?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational research design. This design was used to establish the relationship between Grade 10 learners' academic performance and the variables that influence academic performance in English. It is used in research studies that provide static pictures of situations and establish the relationship between different variables (McBurney & White, 2009). The researcher studied the phenomenon of interest as it exists in descriptive research. Naturally, no attempt is made to manipulate people, circumstances, or events. Correlational study in education seeks traits, abilities, or conditions that co-exist or co-relate. Meanwhile, according to McCombes (2020), a correlational research design measures a relationship between two variables without the researcher controlling either. It sought a positive or negative association. Correlational research examined the relationship between Academic Performance and students' motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning. It is a type of nonexperimental research in which the researcher measures the variables and assesses the statistical relationship (i.e., the correlation) between them with little or no effort to manage extraneous variables.

Respondents

The study participants were Grade 10 language learners at Bukidnon National High School for the school year 2022-2023. There are 41 learners from the Science, Technology, and Engineering (STE) Program and 182 from the Enhanced Basic Education Program (EBEP) Curriculum.

The teacher's Class Record was utilized to identify the number of participants using Slovin's formula, with a total sample size of 143, as shown in the Table below. After determining the number of sample of participants in every section through Slovin's formula, Systematic Random Sampling was employed by researcher. The target participants received a Certificate of Assent and an Informed Consent or Certificate of Consent that their parents had signed. They were given the freedom to decide whether or not to take part in

the study. Hence, they had the option to withdraw whenever needed.

Table 1. *The participants of the study*

<i>Sections</i>	<i>Population (N)</i>	<i>Sample size (n)</i>
Cantoria	41	26
Bangkal	57	37
Golden Trumpet	64	41
Molave	61	39
Total	223	143

Instrument

The study used four sets of questionnaires to measure the participants' level of motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning towards the English language and the influence of learners' academic performance in English. The first questionnaires were adapted from Orwig, C.J. (1995), SIL International Language and Culture Archives, Language Learning Attitudes Questionnaire (What is Wrong With My Attitude?). The other three sets of questionnaires on self-efficacy, attitude, and self-directed learning will be adapted from Teng, K. (1995), Perceptions of Taiwanese Students to English Learning as Functions of Self-Efficacy, Motivation, Learning Activities, and Self-Directed Learning. The researcher added statements to complete each set.

Level of Motivation in English. The first set of questionnaires is ten items per sub-variable on the level of motivation in English. The researcher prepared this questionnaire to determine the learner's level of motivation towards the English language and its influence on learners' academic performance in English. It included the following constructs, listed below with their specific items and the total number of items.

Table 2.

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Questionnaire Item</i>	<i>Total</i>
Intrinsic Goal Orientation	10-item	10
Extrinsic Goal Orientation	10-item	10
Total Number of Items		20

Level of Attitudes in Learning English. The second set of questionnaires is 10-item on the level of attitudes in language learning. The instrument was composed of 3 constructs with the three dimensions of attitude. This measured the learner's level of attitude towards the academic performance in English.

Table 3.

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Questionnaire Item</i>	<i>Total</i>
Affective	5-item	5
Behavioral	4-item	4
Cognitive	1-item	1
Total Number of Items		10

Level of Self-Efficacy. The third set of questionnaires consisted of a 15-item assessment measuring self-efficacy in the English language. This study used a questionnaire to assess students' English language self-efficacy and its impact on academic performance. Below are its structures and things.

Table 4.

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Questionnaire Item</i>	<i>Total</i>
Beliefs	15-item	15
Total Number of Items		15

Level of Self-Directed Learning in English. The fourth set of questionnaires consisted of 15 items per sub-variable, focusing on assessing Self-Directed Learning levels.

The instrument consisted of three constructs, each with their respective subscales. This study assessed the extent to which learners exhibit self-directed learning behaviors concerning the English language and examined the impact of these behaviors on learners' academic performance in English.

Table 5.

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Questionnaire Item</i>	<i>Total</i>
English Learning Outside Classrooms	15 - item	15
Ability in Self-Directed Learning	15 - item	15
Management in Self-Directed English Learning	15 - item	15
Total Number of Items		45

Scoring Procedure

Below are the scoring scales which guided the researcher in determining the following:

Table 6. *Scoring Guide for Language Learning Motivation*

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	3.50-4.49	Agree	High
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral	Moderately High
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Low
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 7. *Scoring Guide for Attitude*

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	90-100	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Positive
4	85-89	Agree	Highly Positive
3	80-84	Neutral	Moderately Positive
2	75-79	Disagree	Negative
1	74-below	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Negative

Table 8. *Scoring Guide for Self-Efficacy*

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	90-100	Always or almost true of me	Excellent
4	3.50-4.49	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
3	2.50-3.49	Somewhat true of me	Moderate
2	1.50-2.49	Usually not true of me	Fair
1	1.00-1.49	Never true of me	Poor

Table 9. *Scoring Guide for Self-Directed Learning*

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	To a very great extent	Very High Skilled
4	3.50-4.49	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
3	2.50-3.49	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
2	1.50-2.49	To a minor extent	Less Skilled
1	1.00-1.49	Not really	Not Skilled

Table 10. *Scoring Guide for Academic Performance*

Grades	Description
90-100	Outstanding
85-89	Very Satisfactory
80-84	Satisfactory
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory
60-74	Did Not Meet Expectations

Procedure

In this study, principles of research ethics were observed. After the research proposal was approved, the principal investigator revised the study following the suggestions and comments made by the panelists. A pilot test was conducted at Bukidnon National High School with thirty (30) Grade 10 English language learners to assess the reliability of the questionnaire. With the result of the pilot test, the investigator compiled the requirements for submission to the Research Ethics Board.

The researcher sought approval to conduct the study from the office of the Dean of the School of Teacher Education. Once approved, this paper was sent to the office of the Director of the Research Ethics Board for review of the ethical standard of the study. Upon compliance, a letter was sent to the Vice President for Research and Extension office of Liceo de Cagayan University. with regard to following the Ethics Research Board protocol.

The researcher then secured the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent, asking permission to administer the survey questionnaires to the target respondents, and retrieved the data. The researcher personally wrote formal letters to the Schools Division Superintendent, asking permission to administer the survey questionnaire to the student participants. The letter's content encompassed the schedule of the study. Once the approval from the Schools Division Superintendent was granted, the researcher met the School principal, bringing the approved letter to ask for support and permission to conduct the study at the school she is leading.

Once approval and consent have been obtained, following health protocol requirements, the researcher met the participants during the scheduled meeting. It should be noted that the principal investigator has no conflict of interest in any form with the sponsor, co-investigators, or study site. In conducting the study, the researcher observed the ethical guidelines set by the University Ethics Review Committee. An informed consent or assent form was distributed to participants first, letting them bring it home with their parents' and legal guardians' permission to participate in the study. In addition, the researcher set another schedule for conducting and administering the research survey questionnaires.

The study applied to the Grade 10 English language learners handled by the researcher. Grade 10 learners not under the class of the researcher and other grade levels, and those who could give informed consent or refused, were excluded and withdrawn from participating as this can interfere with the study outcome. Those who gave their consent were included as participants. The investigator emphasized the participants' voluntary participation and said they could withdraw from participating in the study without incurring any costs. It was entirely up to the individual whether or not to participate in the study. Those who chose to participate were informed of their privacy rights and provided an informed consent form to ensure confidentiality and complete anonymity.

To complete the survey questionnaires, 25–30 minutes were given to each participant to complete them and be guided if they ever had clarifications or queries about some items of the questionnaire. No physical risks were involved, as they only needed to provide their answers in the survey questionnaires. Once finished, the questionnaires were retrieved. The respondents were reminded that all data collected was treated with absolute confidentiality and was used for academic purposes.

An approved letter from the school principal was sent to the registrar, requesting a copy of the second quarter grade in English of the Grade 10 learners handled by the researcher for the School Year 2022-2023.

There was no immediate reward from this study; however, the information gained may aid in investigating the degrees of motivation, attitudes, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning towards the English language and their influence on the learners' academic performance in this subject.

Furthermore, the finalized paper will be made accessible to the participants. Prior to its publication, each respondent's consent was taken into consideration. All information gathered regarding the respondents remained confidential, and the finalized data was transparently disseminated. Code names or numbers were assigned to identify the participants. The researcher took every precaution to ensure the respondents' privacy.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used to facilitate the analysis of the interpretation.

For problems 1 to 5, descriptive statistical analyses were used to get the mean and standard deviation.

In problem 6, the researcher employed Pearson Correlation to ascertain a statistically significant association between the independent variables, namely language learning motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning, and the dependent variable, which pertained to the learners' academic performance.

For problem 7, the researcher utilized Multiple Linear Regression to identify which single or combined variables best predict the English learners' performance. All statistical treatments were carried out through the SPSS software.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyses and interprets the data gathered in the study. The data groups are presented and illustrated following the sequence of the problems stated. In the first part, questions related to the participants' level of motivation in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic. In the second part, questions related to the participant's level of language learning attitude. The third part of the question related to the participants' level of self-efficacy. The fourth part, questions related to the participants' level of self-directed learning in terms of English learning outside the classroom, ability in self-directed English learning, and management in self-directed English learning. The fifth part contains questions related to the participant's level of Academic Performance. In the sixth part, questions related to the significant relationship between the participants' level of Academic Performance in motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed English language learning. The seventh part, related to the questions on the variables, singly or in combination, best predicts the learner's academic performance.

Problem 1. What is the participants' level of motivation in terms of: intrinsic, and extrinsic?

Table 11. *Participants' Level of Motivation in terms of Intrinsic Motivation for English Learning*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. English will help me to advance my studies.	4.34	.844	Agree	High
2. English will help me to get a good job someday.	4.42	.890	Agree	High
3. I want to reach my English learning goals.	4.22	.929	Agree	High
4. I want to talk with English speakers.	3.66	1.05	Agree	High
5. Because I like the language.	3.93	1.02	Agree	High
6. I want to travel in different countries.	4.32	1.02	Agree	High
7. To understand the way of life in the country or countries where English is spoken.	4.00	1.06	Agree	High
8. I would like to live in the country where English is spoken.	3.37	1.23	Neutral	Moderately High
9. Because I am good at it.	2.97	1.02	Neutral	Moderately High
10. Because it is an international language.	3.88	1.14	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	3.91	1.02	Agree	High

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.50–4.49 – Agree, High; 2.50–3.49 – Neutral, Moderately High; 1.50–2.49 – Disagree, Low; 1.00–1.49 – Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 11 presents the Participants' Level of Motivation in terms of Intrinsic Motivation for English Learning. According to the Table, students received the highest mean score of 4.42 for item number 2, "English will help me get a good job someday," and a mean of 4.34 for item number 1, "English will help me advance my studies." Meanwhile, learners obtained the lowest mean score of 2.97 for item 9, "Because I am good at it," followed by item 8, "I would like to live in the country where English is spoken," with a mean of 3.37. The overall mean is 3.91, interpreted as high. This data revealed that the learners are highly motivated to learn English.

This finding is comparable to the claims of Edwards and Johansen (2015). If a person is intrinsically motivated, they will accomplish a task just because it intrigues them. Curiosity, interest, involvement, or a good challenge are all examples of intrinsic motivation. It shows that the learners feel motivated because the action is significant and appears self-sustaining; they are intrinsically motivated. This finding is supported by Al-hairy (2013), Barack et al. (2016), Huang et al. (2017), Kazantseva et al. (2016), Lee (2016), Majid et al. (2012), and Shyan (2016), which state that a productive and interactive learning environment increases learners motivation, especially if the students feel comfortable with what they are doing. The need to interact, to be competent, and to gain autonomy boosts intrinsic motivation.

In addition, the data also show that the highest indicator is the item that states, "English will help me get a good job someday." This finding supports the claims of Siddiqui (2019) that having a workforce that is proficient in English is no longer a luxury; it is now a necessity, and business success depends on how well we do in our language competency. It means that corporations now require a high level of competency or command of the English language; lacking this talent may jeopardize employability in today's globalized workplace. On the contrary, the lowest indicator is the item that states, "Because I am good at it," which indicates moderately high motivation. Goktepe (2013) found that Grade 9 learners at a public high school generally claimed they could not speak English fluently. As a result of these findings, we believe that the learners were aware of the situation. It would mean that speaking English is essential to them; they admit that they do not speak English well but that, with practice, they can improve.

Taylor et al. (2014) found that intrinsic motivation was the primary factor in school accomplishment. Froiland & Worrell (2016) found that intrinsic drive predicts student engagement. This finding would imply that the Grade 10 language learners will show passion, interest, and optimism to the extent that they will progress academically.

Table 12. Participants' Level of Motivation in terms of Extrinsic Motivation for English Learning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Because English is a required course in my School.	3.71	1.14	Agree	High
2. In order to pass an English proficiency test (e.g. TOEFL or any entrance exam.).	3.81	1.11	Agree	High
3. My family wants me to learn English.	3.20	1.22	Neutral	Moderately High
4. I want to get good grades in English.	4.29	1.01	Agree	High
5. Because many friends of mine can speak English.	3.26	1.24	Neutral	Moderately High
6. I would feel ashamed if I couldn't talk to foreigners who speak English.	3.38	1.26	Neutral	Moderately High
7. Because I want to be a good English speaker.	4.12	1.07	Agree	High
8. I want to work abroad.	3.65	1.37	Agree	High
9. I would feel guilty if I do not know how to use the language correctly considering that it is the medium of instruction used in school.	3.82	1.05	Neutral	Moderately High
10. I want to study in an international school.	3.46	1.23	Neutral	Moderately High
Over-all Mean	3.67	1.17	Agree	High

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.50–4.49 – Agree, High; 2.50–3.49 – Neutral, Moderately High; 1.50–2.49 – Disagree, Low; 1.00–1.49 – Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 12 presents the Participants' Level of Motivation in terms of Extrinsic Motivation for English Learning. As shown in the Table, learners obtained the highest mean score of 4.29 for item number 4, "I want to get good grades in English," followed by item number 7, "Because I want to be a good English speaker," with a mean of 4.12. Meanwhile, learners obtained the lowest mean score of 3.20 for item 3, "My family wants me to learn English," followed by item 5, "Because many friends of mine can speak English," with a mean score of 3.26. The overall mean is 3.67, interpreted as high. This data revealed that the learners have high extrinsic motivation for English learning.

This finding provides evidence in line with Cherry's (2018) assertion that extrinsic motivation centers around reinforcement contingencies or external incentives such as grades, acclaim, money, and celebrity. It shows that the learners wanted to study English because of external goals and circumstances allowing them to achieve a specific end. Hajhashemi et al. (2017) state that learners are primarily motivated to engage in activities that demand substantial exertion and diligence. Additionally, it suggests that this applies to all learners, particularly those acquiring English as a second language.

In addition, the highest indicator is the item that states, "I want to get good grades in English." Extrinsic incentives are also positive reinforcement; they help learners comprehend that their performance is excellent or deserving praise. According to a study by Cornell professor C. Kirabo Jackson, students who receive rewards for doing well on AP exams tend to perform better on the SAT and choose to enroll in college at a higher rate than those who do not. It is associated with Meadows-Fernandez's (2017) study, which discovered that extrinsic motivation is a reward-driven action. Extrinsic motivation, awards, or other incentives, such as acclaim, come from fame or money for some pursuits.

On the other hand, extrinsic motivation has been connected to psychological distress and poorer levels of well-being, which may prevent students from engaging in a task and hence reduce students' learning effectiveness (Kuvaas et al., 2017). This statement contradicts the result. Language, we need strategies to find inspiration from outside sources.

Moreover, the data also illustrate the learners' highest mean, an item about "I want to get good grades in English," implying that extrinsically motivated learners consider external factors that influence a need for success towards a specific objective. This motivation comes from an awareness of the real benefits of learning it. Getting good grades is the best factor influencing learners' interest in studying and learning English. On the other hand, the lowest mean is the item "My family wants me to learn English." This finding would mean that the family would be the most minor factor influencing the learners' interest in learning the English language.

Table 13. Summary of Participants' Level of Language Learning Motivation

Sub-variables	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
English Learning Intrinsic Motivation	3.91	1.02	Agree	High
English Learning Extrinsic Motivation	3.67	1.17	Agree	High
Over-all Mean	3.79	1.10	Agree	High

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Strongly Agree, Very High; 3.50–4.49 – Agree, High; 2.50–3.49 – Neutral, Moderately High; 1.50–2.49 – Disagree, Low; 1.00–1.49 – Strongly Disagree, Very Low

Table 13 presents a Summary of Participants' levels of Language Learning Motivation. As shown in the Table, learners obtained the highest mean score of 3.91 for intrinsic motivation in English learning, while they got a mean score of 3.67 for extrinsic motivation. The average mean is 3.79, which is relatively high. The data indicate that the participants exhibit significant motivation for pursuing English language learning, both intrinsically and extrinsically.

This finding supports what Deci and Ryan (2020) say about motivation: It can be a one-dimensional concept that varies in quantity or amount, but it also varies in quality or type of intrinsic motivation (i.e., the motivation that comes from the self or work and is voluntary) and extrinsic motivation (i.e., the motivation that comes from others and is controlled). Intrinsic and extrinsic types of motivation differ not just in their origins but also in their implications for learning and well-being, with more intrinsic forms often demonstrating more adaptive value (Taylor et al., 2014; Howard et al., 2021).

According to the mean, this data show that the learners' intrinsic motivation is higher than their extrinsic motivation. Some researchers have supported this data, asserting that intrinsic motivation is superior to extrinsic motivation. According to Schunk (2014), intrinsic motivation is situational and dynamic. A phenomenon that is inherently inspiring on one occasion may transition into being externally motivating on a subsequent occasion. Extrinsic rewards do not negatively affect intrinsic motivation. The activity determines the inner and extrinsic drive. As a result, one's ability to retain intrinsic desire is unquestionably a strength. For example, if an employer constantly compliments his employee on his daily chores, the employee will be less intrinsically motivated to complete this work in the future (Cherry, 2016).

The data also emphasize that the learners have a high level of motivation for English Language learning, both intrinsic and extrinsic. According to a survey, most learners have a defined study motivation toward the English language. Learners can understand the significance of learning English. In addition, students' interest in English influences their learning motivation and accomplishment. Learners with solid learning motivation approach their studies positively and make significant efforts to grasp English with precise aim and desire, resulting in a higher grade.

Problem 2. What is the participants' level of learning attitude in terms of: Affective, Behavioral, and Cognitive?

Table 14. Participants' Level of Language Learning Attitude in Terms of Affective

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I don't worry a lot about making mistakes.	2.15	1.14	Disagree	Highly Negative
2. I'm not afraid people will laugh at me if I don't say things right.	2.36	1.24	Neutral	Highly Negative
3. I end up not trembling and practically not in a cold sweat when I have to talk in front of people.	2.72	1.16	Neutral	Moderately Positive
4. It is a mark of respect to people to learn their language if you're living in their country.	3.79	1.04	Agree	Highly Positive
5. Speaking the language of the community where I'll be living will let me help people more than I could otherwise.	3.57	1.05	Agree	Highly Positive
Over-all Mean	2.92	1.13	Neutral	Moderately Positive

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Strongly Agree, Very Highly Positive; 3.50–4.49 – Agree, Highly Positive; 2.50–3.49 – Neutral, Moderately Positive; 1.50–2.49 – Disagree, Highly Negative; 1.00–1.49 – Strongly Disagree, Very Highly Negative

Table 14 presents the Participants' Level of Language Learning Attitude in terms of affective. As shown in the Table, learners obtained the highest mean score of $M = 3.79$ and $SD = 1.04$ for item number 4 "It is a mark of respect for people to learn their language if you are living in their country." On the other hand, learners obtained the lowest mean score of $M = 2.15$ and $SD = 1.14$ for item number 1, "I do not worry a lot about making mistakes." The overall mean is 2.92, described as neutral and interpreted as moderately positive. This data revealed that learners' attitudes regarding effective learning were moderately positive.

The data illustrate the significance of learning English in the community, in the country, and outside the country. Alam (2017) claims

that attitudes toward a language are critical to language learning. This finding is especially true when one lives in an English-speaking community or country since one may express respect and offer assistance because one understands the value of language.

The study by Ryan and Giles (2018) claims that language attitudes are any of a person's emotive, cognitive, or behavioral indexes of evaluative reactions. Thus, Table 14 also illustrates the lowest mean for items that include feelings and emotions of being worried and scared if they commit language mistakes. In addition, language learners may adopt a range of attitudes regarding language acquisition, according to Arda and Doylan (2017).

Furthermore, the learners' attitude towards the English language in terms of effect is interpreted as moderately positive. The Nyamubi (2016) study found a positive correlation between students' performance in the language and their attitudes toward it when it came to their attitudes toward English and their proficiency in it.

Bloom discovered that emotional factors boost cognitive achievement in the relevant area by roughly a quarter, implying that affective features account for about a quarter of the variability in learning success.

Table 15. *Participants' Level of Language Learning Attitude in Terms of Behavioral*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Learning a language may be important to my goals and I do expect it to be much fun.	2.63	1.00	Neutral	Moderately Positive
2. I do have any idea about how to go about learning a language.	2.86	1.18	Neutral	Moderately Positive
6. I find it easy to make conversation even with people who speak my own language.	2.72	1.30	Neutral	Moderately Positive
9. In school, if I didn't know an answer for sure, I'd sometimes answer out loud in class anyway.	3.00	1.05	Neutral	Moderately Positive
Over-all Mean	2.80	1.14	Neutral	Moderately Positive

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Strongly Agree, Very Highly Positive; 3.50–4.49 – Agree, Highly Positive; 2.50–3.49 – Neutral, Moderately Positive; 1.50–2.49 – Disagree, Highly Negative; 1.00–1.49 – Strongly Disagree, Very Highly Negative

Table 15 presents the Participants' Level of Language Learning Attitude regarding behavior. As shown in the Table, learners obtained the highest mean score of $M = 3.00$, $SD = 1.05$ for item number 9: "In school, if I did not know an answer for sure, I would sometimes answer out loud in class anyway." On the other hand, learners obtained the lowest mean score of $M = 2.63$ and $SD = 1.00$ for item number 1: "Learning a language may be important to my goals, and I do expect it to be much fun." The overall mean is 2.80, described as neutral and interpreted as moderately positive. This data revealed that learners were moderately positive in their attitudes in terms of behavioral learning.

This finding supported the claim of Sicam and Lucas' (2016) that Filipino bilingual learners have very positive attitudes toward English. Positive in the sense that the general views of English language learners toward the language demonstrated that they are aware of the personal effects of English in their lives. They concluded that favorable attitudes have remained consistent over time.

The highest indicator is the item that states, "In school, if I did not know an answer for sure, I would sometimes answer out loud in class anyway." This is supported by Abidin et al. (2012), who argue that the behavioral element concerns how an individual behaves and reacts in specific situations. In other words, behavioral refers to the proclivity to adopt new learning practices. On the other hand, the lowest indicator is the item that states, "Learning a language may be important to my goals, and I do expect it to be much fun." Avila (2016), who emphasized that teachers should make learning activities more enjoyable, supports this. Educators can consider viable and creative teaching approaches to overcome students' learning challenges, such as a need for more interest and attention to the subject. This means that the most crucial thing, however, is that learners view every learning process as enjoyable. It might make the learners feel more at ease during the learning process. Fun learning exercises will have a natural impact on enhancing learners' English abilities.

PATT studies have found the behavioral component lacking (Ankiewicz, 2019). Autio et al. (2019) incorporated the examination of conduct by interpreting questions that evaluate a student's readiness to engage in action. This research employed a similar approach by utilizing the theoretical construct of behavioral intention and reinterpreting items within the career domain as manifestations of such intention, as demonstrated in the work of Summers and Abd-El-Khalick (2018).

Table 16. *Participants' Level of Language Learning Attitude in Terms of Cognitive*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
10. I often think out loud, trying out my ideas on other people.	3.43	1.20	Neutral	Moderately Positive
Over-all Mean	3.43	1.20	Neutral	Moderately Positive

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Strongly Agree, Very Highly Positive; 3.50–4.49 – Agree, Highly Positive; 2.50–3.49 – Neutral, Moderately Positive; 1.50–2.49 – Disagree, Highly Negative; 1.00–1.49 – Strongly Disagree, Very Highly Negative

Table 16 presents the Participants' Level of Language Learning Attitude in terms of cognitive. As shown in the table, learners obtained an overall mean score of $M = 3.43$ and $SD = 1.20$ for item number 10, "I often think out loud, trying out my ideas on other people," described as neutral and interpreted as moderately positive. This data revealed that learners were moderately positive in their attitudes in terms of cognitive learning.

Abidin et al. (2012) emphasized that beliefs, thoughts, or perceptions about the object of the attitude comprise the cognitive component that supports the information revealed. This attitude component in the language learning process comprises language learners' beliefs about the knowledge they have received and understood. The cognitive attitude is divided into four stages: a) linking previous knowledge with new knowledge; b) developing new knowledge; c) testing new knowledge; and d) applying new knowledge in various settings. This means that if the learners can undergo these four stages, then language learning is automatically found to be effective.

The only indicator for this domain is the item that states, "I often think out loud; trying out my ideas on other people is interpreted as moderately positive. Main (2014), who emphasized that an individual's mental disposition and a response or reaction to the object of the attitude influence individual action, supports this finding. This description is consistent with Jung's definition of attitude, a "readiness of the psyche to act or react in a certain way." However, experiences from the past and present are what give rise to such an attitude.

In addition, Abun (2018) went deeper into the construction of attitude, claiming that attitude is formed through culture. He believes that the culture in which one is raised shapes one's mindset.

Furthermore, according to Ankiewicz's (2019) paradigm, the cognitive component influences the affective component, and the two parts affect the behavioral component further.

Table 17. Summary of the Participants' Level of Language Learning Attitude

Sub-Construct	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Affective	2.92	1.13	Neutral	Moderately Positive
Behavioral	2.80	1.14	Neutral	Moderately Positive
Cognitive	2.43	1.20	Neutral	Moderately Positive
Over-all Mean	2.72	1.16	Neutral	Moderately Positive

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Strongly Agree, Very Highly Positive; 3.50–4.49 – Agree, Highly Positive; 2.50–3.49 – Neutral, Moderately Positive; 1.50–2.49 – Disagree, Highly Negative; 1.00–1.49 – Strongly Disagree, Very Highly Negative

Table 17 summarizes the participants' level of language learning attitude. As depicted in the table, the sub-construct affective obtained the highest mean of $M = 2.92$, $SD = 1.13$, followed by the behavioral sub-construct with a mean of $M = 2.80$, $SD = 1.1$, and last is cognitive with a mean score of $M = 2.43$, $SD = 1.43$. The overall mean is $M = 2.72$ and $SD = 1.16$, described as neutral and interpreted as moderately positive. This data revealed that learners were moderately positive in their attitudes in terms of cognitive learning.

Most research studies examining attitudes' behavioral, cognitive, and emotional components support the findings. Tanni (2015) defines attitudes as having behavioral, cognitive, and affective components. These three attitudes could have resulted from the same experience.

Effectiveness is the highest of the three domains, followed by behavioral and cognitive. This means that in a given scenario, they can interact and overlap, but one of them is usually the dominant predictor of how one feels about it.

Problem 3. What is the participants' level of self-efficacy?

Table 18. Participants' Level of Language Learning Self-Efficacy

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. If I study hard, I can learn English well.	3.95	1.24	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
2. I enjoy learning English.	3.94	.948	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
3. Learning English is important for me.	3.65	1.20	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
4. My work will be helped by learning English.	3.81	1.14	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
5. I am satisfied with my English listening ability.	3.41	1.11	Somewhat true of me	Moderate
6. I am satisfied with my English-speaking ability.	3.25	1.06	Somewhat true of me	Moderate
7. I am satisfied with my English reading ability.	3.91	.980	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
8. I am satisfied with my English writing ability.	3.09	1.21	Somewhat true of me	Moderate
9. I have had good English learning experience before.	3.44	1.15	Somewhat true of me	Moderate
10. I am happy about my effort in English learning.	3.68	1.08	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
11. Everyone can learn English well.	3.64	1.34	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
12. English learning effort is worth the time spent.	4.01	1.06	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
13. Making mistakes in speaking and writing English is okay with me.	3.68	1.22	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
14. I am happy listening to fluent English speakers.	4.14	1.07	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
15. English learning is fun and inspiring.	4.05	1.09	Usually true of me	Satisfactory
Over-all Mean	3.71	1.12	Usually true of me	Satisfactory

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Always or almost true of me, Excellent; 3.50–4.49 – Usually true of me, Satisfactory; 2.50–3.49 – Somewhat true of me, Moderate; 1.50–2.49 – Usually not true of me, Fair; 1.00–1.49 – Never true of me, Poor

As shown in Table 18, learners obtained the highest mean score of 4.14 for item 14, "I am happily listening to fluent English speakers," followed by item 15, "English learning is fun and inspiring," with a mean score of 4.05, and item 12, "English learning effort is worth the time spent," with a mean score of 4.01. On the other hand, learners obtained the lowest mean score of 3.09 for item number 8, "I am satisfied with my English writing ability," followed by item number 6, "I am satisfied with my English-speaking ability," with a mean score of 3.25, and item number 5, "I am satisfied with my English listening ability," with a mean score of 3.41. The overall mean is 3.71, interpreted as satisfactory. This data revealed that learners have satisfactory self-efficacy toward language learning.

This states that self-efficacy relates to people's confidence to complete and perform specific actions. This conviction will have an impact on their performance on those tasks. This discovery suggests that individuals with a strong sense of self-efficacy are more likely to exhibit success and motivation, thereby increasing their likelihood of achieving their goals.

According to the learners' subjective observations and personal experiences, Table 6 gives a general overview of their perceived capacity or aptitude for successful language acquisition. Hence, self-efficacy beliefs influence individuals' emotions, cognition, motivation, and behavior. Bandura's social cognition theory states that self-efficacy and self-esteem help learners achieve their goals. Prior performance, peer comparison, and learning environment feedback affect students' self-efficacy and self-esteem (Namaziandost & Akmak, 2020).

According to Bryant (2017), Bandura posits that four resources can aid in the cultivation of students' self-efficacy. Operational, mastery, social, vicarious, and physiological aspects influence self-efficacy. The data in Table 18 shows that most items are satisfactory and four are moderate. Self-efficacy is crucial because Henry Ford famously said that whether you feel you can or cannot, you are accurate. Moreover, Gandhi recognized the critical role that self-belief plays in our lives. Psychologists have studied the association between high self-efficacy and accomplishment (Moyano et al., 2020). Data also shows that students have enough language self-efficacy. This confirmed that several studies have found a positive association between self-efficacy and academic success. Learners with high academic self-efficacy also have a higher academic status than those with low academic self-efficacy (Ahmad & Safaria, 2013; Pavani & Agrawal, 2015; Hassan et al., 2015; Koseoglu, 2015; Arbabisarjou et al., 2016; Eny & Pujar, 2017). Therefore, engaging in extracurricular English language learning activities within academia can be beneficial as they provide learners with practical exposure to the language (Chakraborty et al., 2021). Therefore, extracurricular activities have an impact on high school students who are English language learners.

Problem 4. What is the participants' level of self-directed learning in terms of: outside learning, ability, and management?

Table 19. *Participants' Level of Self-Directed Learning in Terms of Outside Learning*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I listen to radio programs regularly.	2.50	1.02	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
2. When I speak English TV programs or movies, I pay attention to the contents.	3.49	1.00	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
3. I read English newspapers and magazines regularly.	2.43	1.03	To a minor extent	Less Skilled
4. I write e-mails or correspond with others in English.	2.89	1.18	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
5. I keep a personal journal in English.	2.71	1.19	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
6. I seek opportunities to speak English outside classrooms.	3.22	1.14	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
7. I often use sources on the internet to learn English.	3.83	1.09	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
8. I go to private English schools to learn English.	2.18	1.28	To a minor extent	Less Skilled
9. I work to learn how to pronounce English words.	3.55	1.15	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
10. I speak English with my friends most of the times.	3.01	1.33	Usually true of me	Moderately Skilled
11. I use English in conversing with my family most of the times.	2.49	1.26	To a minor extent	Less Skilled
12. I watch English language films.	4.16	1.16	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
13. I read English novels and consult dictionary at the same time.	3.35	1.26	Somewhat true of me	Moderately Skilled
14. I listen and sing English songs.	4.42	.978	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
15. I play board word games like scrabble, word factory and others.	3.65	1.27	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
Over-all Mean	3.19	1.12	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – To a very great extent, Very Highly Skilled; 3.50–4.49 – To a great extent, Highly Skilled; 2.50–3.49 – To a moderate extent, Moderately Skilled; 1.50–2.49 – To a minor extent, Less Skilled; 1.00–1.49 – Not Really, Poor

Table 19 depicts the Participants' Level of Self-Directed Learning in Terms of Outside Learning. Item 14, "I listen to and sing English songs," received the highest mean score from students (4.42), while item 12, "I watch English language films," received a mean of 4.16. Item number 7: "I often use sources on the internet to learn English," with a mean of 3.83. On the other hand, learners obtained the lowest mean score of 2.18 for item number 8, "I go to private English schools to learn English," followed by item number 3, "I read English newspapers and magazines regularly," with a mean score of 2.43, and item number 11, "I use English in conversing with my family most of the time," with a mean score of 2.49. The overall mean is 3.19, interpreted as moderately skilled. This data revealed that the learners were moderately skilled in self-directed learning in terms of outdoor learning.

This finding supported the claims of Larsen, Walsh, Almond, & Myers (2017), which emphasize that outside-of-the-classroom teaching and learning events have several advantages for both students and teachers. When students put what they have learned "in the real world" into practice, the result is a student-centered learning experience that increases learning and promotes personal and social growth. Furthermore, learners who participate in learning experiences outside the classroom report higher motivation levels, better recall of course material, and higher academic accomplishment (Takeuchi et al., 2016; Ryan & Deci, 2017).

The data illustrate that among the 15 items, listening to and singing English songs got the highest mean, followed by watching English-language films. Alisa and Nihada (2016) studied the impact of music and songs on learners and their role in increasing motivation. The study revealed that songs positively impact the learners' vocabulary, pronunciation, and genuine sense of words.

This result is comparable to one from Haghverdi's (2015) study on the influence of music and film on high school students' linguistic

achievement. The study examined how movies and songs about language acquisition and achievement affect language learning. It also sought to pinpoint particular skills that watching movies and listening to music can enhance. Music aids in the acquisition of new vocabulary. This study concluded that the significance of movies and music in learners' language acquisition is critical and considerably impacts students' language achievement. Music aids in the acquisition of new vocabulary. This study concluded that the significance of movies and music in students' language acquisition is critical and considerably impacts students' language achievement.

Furthermore, the data revealed that the learners are moderately skilled in self-directed learning outside of school. This finding means that several learners attempt to develop their foreign language skills outside of the classroom in a self-directed manner. According to Lai et al. (2022), learners use mobile apps like HelloTalk, Twitter, and YouTube to construct their learning environment. Teachers may help, but the process is self-directed.

Table 20. *Participants' Level of Self-Directed Learning in Terms of Ability*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I know how to learn English well.	3.60	.975	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
2. I can use many different resources to aid my English learning.	3.69	.982	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
3. I can search for new information to help my English learning.	4.00	.981	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
4. I apply what I have learned in English for writing and conversation.	3.98	.955	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
5. I can learn English independently.	3.48	1.12	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
6. I know how to solve English learning problems when I encounter them.	3.37	1.02	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
7. I practice speaking English when I can.	4.03	1.00	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
8. I use English immersion.	3.17	.927	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
9. I have an idea on how to learn the language easily.	3.43	.994	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
10. I learn with English music.	4.11	1.00	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
11. I stay motivated to learn no matter what the circumstances may arise.	3.81	1.01	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
12. I listen to anything and everything in English.	3.83	1.01	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
13. I always practice speaking in English.	3.57	1.13	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
14. I make flashcards.	2.57	1.22	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
15. I watch YouTube, TV Shows and Movies.	4.30	1.03	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
Over-all Mean	3.66	1.02	To a great extent	Highly Skilled

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – To a very great extent, Very Highly Skilled; 3.50–4.49 – To a great extent, Highly Skilled; 2.50–3.49 – To a moderate extent, Moderately Skilled; 1.50–2.49 – To a minor extent, Less Skilled; 1.00–1.49 – Not Really, Poor

Table 20 depicts the Participants' Level of Self-Directed Learning in Terms of Ability. As shown in the Table, learners obtained the highest mean score of 4.30 for item number 15, "I watch YouTube, TV Shows, and Movies," followed by item number 10, "I learn with English music," with a mean score of 4.11, and item number 7, "I practice speaking English when I can," with a mean score of 4.03. On the other hand, students received the lowest mean score of 2.57 for item number 14, "I make flashcards," followed by item number 8, "I use English immersion," with a mean score of 3.17, and item number 6, "I know how to solve English learning problems when I encounter them," with a mean score of 3.37. The overall mean is 3.66, which is interpreted as highly skilled. The data presented in this study indicate that the learners exhibited a high level of proficiency in self-directed learning, specifically in terms of their abilities.

This result aligns with the assertions of Zhang and Pérez-Paredes (2019), who posit that learners exhibit self-directed learning behavior when initiating learning tasks but do not actively engage in self-regulated learning. Learners can utilize mobile technology to facilitate the acquisition of foreign languages, thereby fostering a self-directed learning approach. Sung et al. (2015) suggest using Google or YouTube to obtain language resources and practice opportunities anytime, anyplace. With its individualism feature, mobile technology enables learners to personalize and adjust the learning process depending on their requirements and interests.

The data illustrate that the learners are highly skilled in self-directed learning in terms of ability. Consequently, Curry et al. (2017) found that SDL-controlled language learners are more likely to succeed in resources, techniques, and learning outcomes. This discovery implies that, while learners perform SDLL, teachers continue to play a vital role. As indicated by the SDLL conducted about technology (Lai et al., 2017; Sert & Boynuegri, 2017), teachers may play a more critical social role.

Moreover, the finding in Table 8 revealed that among the 15 items for ability in self-directed learning, watching YouTube, TV Shows, and Movies obtained the highest mean score of 4.30, which implies that using mobile technology is evident. A study by Haidari et al. (2019) discovered that technology significantly influences learners' abilities. As a result, teachers' ability to use technology to aid students' language acquisition is crucial in the new standard setting, where students do online classes and rarely meet their teachers. ESL students also learn SDL student-centeredly. Actively learning a language helps ESL students find useful tools.

Table 21 depicts the Participants' Level of Self-Directed Learning in Terms of Management. As shown in the table, learners obtained the highest mean score of 4.00 for item number 2, "I manage my English learning process," followed by item number 3, "I have plans for my English learning," with a mean of 3.65. Item number 5: "I always reach my English learning goals," with a mean score of 3.55. On the other hand, learners obtained the lowest mean score of 2.93 for item number 10, "I make an English Study Plan," followed by item number 13. "I manage my time in learning English wisely," with a mean score of 3.18, and item number 12, "I look for new

techniques on how to learn English effectively," with a mean score of 3.21. The overall mean is 3.37, interpreted as moderately skilled. This data revealed that the learners as a whole were moderately skilled in self-directed learning in terms of management.

Table 21. *Participants' Level of Self-Directed Learning in Terms of Management*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I know my English learning goals.	3.22	1.19	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
2. I manage my English learning process.	4.00	1.05	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
3. I have plans for my English learning.	3.65	.979	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
4. I evaluate my English learning outcomes regularly.	3.46	.969	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
5. I always reach my English learning goals.	3.55	1.01	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
6. I learn English every day outside English classes.	3.30	1.03	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
7. I try to relax when I talk in English.	3.50	1.01	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
8. I can manage to speak the language with foreigners.	3.37	1.18	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
9. I measure my progress in learning English.	3.31	1.12	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
10. I make an English Study Plan.	2.93	1.20	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
11. I find time to engage in any language activities.	3.25	1.06	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
12. I look for new techniques on how to learn English effectively.	3.21	1.13	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
13. I manage my time in learning English wisely.	3.18	1.14	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
14. I create a schedule for the activities that I need to do in a week.	3.29	1.18	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
15. I establish a bond with my friends who are also learning English language.	3.37	1.10	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
Over-all Mean	3.37	1.09	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – To a very great extent, Very Highly Skilled; 3.50–4.49 – To a great extent, Highly Skilled; 2.50–3.49 – To a moderate extent, Moderately Skilled; 1.50–2.49 – To a minor extent, Less Skilled; 1.00–1.49 – Not Really, Poor

This finding supported the claim of Demir (2015), which states that learners understand that they are responsible for their learning rather than relying on an outside source. An active participant in the learning processes, such as gathering knowledge, planning, and assessing the learning activities, is typically referred to as a self-directed learner. According to Yilmaz (2016), implementing active learning techniques can increase learner engagement and improve learning outcomes and performance. Emphasized by Ibrahim et al. (2017), learner self-direction—also known as learning responsibility—refers to a student's preferences.

The data demonstrate that the learners possess a moderate level of proficiency in self-directed learning about their management abilities. This finding would imply that the learners need to improve, especially on items such as making a study plan in English, managing time in learning English wisely, and looking for new techniques to learn English effectively, which obtained the lowest mean as revealed in the data. Saeid and Eslaminejad (2016) found an association between academic success, self-directed learning, and learning readiness. Suknaisith (2014) found that university students liked self-directed learning (SDL). Malison et al. (2018) found that SDL promotes purposeful learning, open-mindedness, self-discipline and self-management, and a strong desire to learn.

This discovery is similar to multiple studies linking self-directed learning (SDL) to academic success: Cazan and Schiopca (2013) found that SDL predicts academic success; Khiat (2014) found SDL boosts academic achievement; SDL, according to Tekkol and Demiral (2018), greatly influences university students' academic performance has a correlation between academic achievement, self-directed learning, and learning readiness; Suknaisith (2014) found that university students liked SDL; and lastly, Malison et al. (2018) found that SDL is connected with beneficial outcomes such deliberate learning, open-mindedness, self-discipline and self-management, and a strong desire to learn.

Table 22. *Summary of Self-Directed Learning*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Outside Learning	3.19	1.12	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
Ability	3.66	1.02	To a great extent	Highly Skilled
Management	3.37	1.09	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled
Over-all Mean	3.41	1.08	To a moderate extent	Moderately Skilled

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – To a very great extent, Very Highly Skilled; 3.50–4.49 – To a great extent, Highly Skilled; 2.50–3.49 – To a moderate extent, Moderately Skilled; 1.50–2.49 – To a minor extent, Less Skilled; 1.00–1.49 – Not Really, Poor

Table 22 presents a summary of the Participants' Level of Self-Directed Learning. As shown in the table, learners obtained the highest mean score of 3.66 for the ability component, 3.37 for management, and last for outdoor learning, with a mean score of 3.19. The overall mean is 3.41, interpreted as moderately skilled. This results showed moderate self-directed learning skills across all three components.

This study supports Merriam and Bierema (2013)'s self-directed learning claims that in its most complete form, self-directed learning encompasses the actions undertaken by individuals to assume accountability and take initiative in their learning endeavors. These actions encompass various aspects, such as identifying personal learning requirements, formulating learning strategies, locating relevant learning resources, employing suitable learning approaches, and assessing the outcomes of their learning experiences, either with or without external assistance.

The data presented in this study provide an overview of self-directed English learning with external learning, proficiency, and self-

management. The data indicate that the learners possess a moderate level of proficiency in self-directed learning, which encompasses all three components. Cremersac et al.'s (2014) research supports the idea that modern people must engage in lifelong learning to adapt to the demands of their professional trajectories and academic pursuits. In higher education, students must actively pursue direct learning experiences. Collaborative learning and working can lead to it. This finding supported the claims of Dent & Koenka (2016) and Jansen et al. (2019) that self-directed learning focuses on self-regulated learning rather than student-initiated learning. Given the importance of this type of learning technique, there is a need for more study on learner-initiated self-directed learning outside of class. Based on the results, the Grade 10 learners have higher SDL ability, which means they established clear learning goals.

Dimaculangan and Dimaculangan (2018) found that language learning strategies promote self-directed learning in two Filipino adult language learners. Moreover, EFL learners find it easier to transfer new information under varying conditions (Daguay-James & Bulusan, 2020). Self-directed learning puts the responsibility for education on the learner, according to Boyer et al. (2015). This procedure requires active learner engagement and control. Avdal (2013) further states that self-directed learners determine learning goals, appropriate learning materials, adequate learning methodologies, and time management to evaluate students' achievements.

Problem 5. What is the participants' level of Academic Performance?

Table 23. Participants' Level of Academic Performance

Grades Range	Description	f	%	Mean	SD	Interpretation
90-100	Outstanding	141	72.3			
85-89	Very Satisfactory	43	22.05			
80-84	Satisfactory	11	5.64			
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	0		92.03	3.88	Outstanding
60-74	Did Not Meet Expectations	0				
	Total	195	100			

Table 23 presents the Participants' Level of Academic Performance. As shown in the table, 72.3% of the learners have outstanding academic performance, 22.05% have a very satisfactory performance, and 5.64% have a satisfactory performance. The overall mean is 92.03, interpreted as outstanding. This data revealed that the level of learners' academic performance is outstanding.

This finding supported the claim of Racca, R.M.A. et al. (2016), who discovered a significant association between students' English language proficiency and academic performance in all courses where English is used as a teaching medium. This fact accords with the conclusions of Ghenhesh P. (2015), who discovered a significant but moderately positive relationship between students' English competence and overall academic success.

Table 23 revealed that the level of learners' academic performance is outstanding. This finding supported the claims of Bornfreund, Cook, Lieberman, & Lowenberg (2015) that because the number of students identified as English Language Learners (ELL) has grown across the country, many states have implemented practices to ensure that all learners, including English language learners, are performing academically at levels. Thus, it will ensure readiness and success as they prepare for continued learning experiences based on college and career readiness standards as they progress through school.

In addition, several research studies have found that English language ability is an essential determinant of overseas learners' academic achievement in institutions where English is the medium of instruction (Cloate, 2016; Kaliyadan et al., 2015; Daller & Phelan, 2013).

Furthermore, several local studies demonstrate that Filipinos are fluent in English. The Education First Index showed these findings as well. Educators agree that mastering the English language is the foundation for academic success. Reading, writing, and working with numbers are all language-based tasks. Similarly, the Department of Education strongly emphasizes students' needs and ensures they acquire English to the fullest extent possible per the K-12 basic education system (Cabigon, 2015).

Many studies have been undertaken that have linked students' English Language Proficiency to their academic success, with the belief that if learners were strong at using English, they would flourish academically.

Problem 6. Is there a significant relationship between the participants' level of Academic Performance in terms of: motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning towards English language?

Table 24 presents the Results of the Pearson Correlation Analysis for the Significant Relationship between the Participants' Academic Performance, Motivation, Attitude, Self-Efficacy, and Self-directed Learning levels. As depicted in the table, the variables, namely intrinsic motivation ($p > .05$), extrinsic motivation ($p > .05$), attitude ($p > .05$), and management ($p > .05$), have probability values more significant than the alpha value of 0.05, indicating that there was no significant relationship between learners' academic performance and the said four variables.

This means these four variables have no significant correlation with learners' academic performance. Meanwhile, the three variables, namely, self-efficacy ($r = .246, p.05$), outside learning ($r = .156, p.05$), and ability ($r = .230, p.05$), have probability values lower than the alpha value of 0.05. This suggests that the three variables affect students' academic achievement. Further, self-efficacy, outside learning, and learners' talents can improve academic achievement.

Table 24. Results of Pearson Correlation Analysis for the Significant Relationship between the Participants' Level of Academic Performance, Motivation, Attitude, Self-Efficacy, and Self-directed Learning

Variable	N	R	P-value	Interpretation
Intrinsic Motivation	.195	.130	.070	Not Significant
Extrinsic Motivation	195	.045	.536	Not Significant
Attitude	195	-.062	.387	Not Significant
Self-Efficacy	195	.246(*)	.001	Significant
Outside Learning	195	.156(*)	.029	Significant
Ability	195	.230(*)	.001	Significant
Management	195	.109	.128	Not Significant

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results of the current study align with the absence of a significant relationship between academic performance and The present outcome confirms the conclusions drawn by Abu Bakar et al. (2012) in their study, which aimed to investigate the correlations between students' academic achievement, attitude, and motivation for success. According to the study, there is a weak and unfavorable correlation between students' achievement motivation and their academic success. Additionally, it is noted that students who have unfavorable attitudes about educational activities engage in challenging behaviors, such as antisocial and off-task behavior (Awang et al., 2013). SDL also affects academic performance, according to Khiat (2014). Thus, educators should boost Grade 10 language learners' learning self-efficacy to increase academic success. The new study also suggests that Grade 10 language learners will go to any lengths to learn if they love it, holding themselves responsible for their development.

This study supports Namaziandost and Cakmak's (2020) argument that learners' self-efficacy and self-esteem might fluctuate depending on past performance, peer comparison, and learning environment feedback. Bandura's social cognitive theory states that self-efficacy and self-esteem are essential to educational success. The impact of self-directed learning on students' motivation for academic achievement and self-efficacy is substantial. Teaching these techniques at the beginning of the session can significantly boost student achievement. The learner's self-direction focuses on the learner's desire or preference, or, in other words, learning responsibility (Ibrahim et al., 2017).

Moreover, numerous studies already connect self-efficacy and English academic success. Several psychologists have examined the hypothesis that higher degrees of self-efficacy boost one's perception of achievement (Moyano et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2020). Hajloo (2014) referenced the fact that self-esteem and achievement are inextricably linked. Higher perceived self-efficacy leads to more effort and tenacity in completing a task, whereas low self-efficacy leads to discouragement and quitting (Yazon, 2015)

Problem 7. Which of the variables, singly or in combination, best predicts the learners' academic performance?

Table 25. Results of the Multiple Regression Analysis for Variables, Singly or in Combination, Best Predicts the Learners' Academic Performance

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	86.503	2.34		36.91	.000	
Intrinsic Motivation	.039	.614	.006	.063	.950	Not Significant
Extrinsic Motivation	-.408	.534	-.075	-.765	.445	Not Significant
Attitude	-.726	.539	-.106	-1.34	.180	Not Significant
Self-Efficacy	1.252	.457	.212	2.73	.007	Significant
Outside Learning	-.060	.642	-.009	-.093	.926	Not Significant
Ability	1.988	.816	.308	2.43	.016	Significant
Management	-.703	.650	-.116	-1.08	.281	Not Significant
	R=.336		R2=.113	F=3.40	P=.002	

Table 25 presents the Results of the Multiple Regression Analysis for variables, singly or in combination, that best predict the learners' academic performance. The Table shows that the R-value of .336 indicates a weak positive relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The R2 value of .113 revealed that the seven independent variables used to predict learners' academic performance explained only 11.3% of learners' academic performance variability. Likewise, the p-value for the computed value of F is .002, lower than the alpha value of 0.05, indicating a significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The multiple regression analysis results revealed that the variables, namely intrinsic motivation ($p > .05$), extrinsic motivation ($p > .05$), attitude ($p > .05$), outside learning ($p > .05$), and management ($p > .05$), significantly failed to predict learners' academic performance. The best predictor of the learners' academic performance is ability (beta = .308, $p > .05$), followed by self-efficacy (beta = .212, $p > .05$).

The regression equation model of this study is $Y = 86.503 + 1.98X_1 + 1.25X_2$

Where

Y- is the learners' academic performance
86.503-B Constant

X1-Ability X2-Self-Efficacy

The regression equation model implied that for every one-point increase in the learners' ability, their academic performance would increase by 1.98. For every one-point increase in the learners' self-efficacy, their academic performance will increase by 1.25.

Multiple research investigations found an association between self-directed learning (SDL) and academic success: Cazan and Schiopca (2013) found that SDL predicts academic success; Dawson et al. (2012) found that technology and SDL are closely related; and Rashid and Asghar (2016) reported a substantial association between information and communication technology (ICT) and SDL.

Ability in self-directed English learning was a significant predictor of the academic performance of Grade 10 language learners. This result is comparable to the study of Prestridge (2012), who claims that ICT and SDL have a strong relationship because ICT is also employed in educational settings. Almost all aspects of life are connected to the use of ICT (Mareco, 2017). Similar to how it is in regular classes, homework is provided after instruction. They can evaluate their IQ (Asfar & Zainuddin, 2015). Learners can improve and advance their SDL skills by utilizing ICT. Learners work with peers from the same setting and converse internationally through ICT. Thus, learners become self-directed, independent lifelong learners, according to Saxena (2013).

Additionally, it was found that self-efficacy plays a crucial role in predicting the academic achievement of Grade 10 language learners. This discovery aligns with previous studies. For instance, Köseolu (2015), Dogan (2015), Sharma (2014), and other researchers have examined this topic. The study found that self-efficacy played a crucial role in predicting the academic performance of Grade 10 language learners. The result is comparable to the studies of Richardson et al. (2012) and Schneider and Preckel (2017), in which a large portion of the study has been devoted to understanding the factors that influence academic accomplishment in settings related to higher education for many years.

Moreover, self-efficacy has repeatedly surfaced as one of these determinants that significantly impacts motivation (Honicke & Broadbent, Citation 2016; Richardson et al., Citation 2012). While empirical evidence continues to corroborate this association, correlational and cross-sectional data tend to reflect it. Furthermore, more scholarly research examining the relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance substantiates this association (Talsma et al., 2018). It implies that self-efficacy increases classroom participation, study effort, perseverance, and reduces negative emotional responses to obstacles.

Conclusions

The current study explored learners' language learning motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning in English. The study determined the level of learners' motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed learning toward their academic performance in English subjects. Their second-quarter English grades were used to measure their academic performance.

Grade 10 learners' disposition to engage in language learning activities toward their academic performance resulted in different levels based on the scoring guide procedure. It indicates that the learners' level of motivation in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, level of language learning attitude, and level of self-directed English learning in terms of management do not significantly influence their disposition to engage in language learning activities toward their academic performance. This finding means that the learners will continue to develop their high level of motivation by maintaining a positive attitude with clear goals and ambitions for acquiring English. The general attitudes of the learners toward the language revealed that they need to improve and be conscious of the individual consequences of English in their lives. This result would further mean that the Grade 10 learners must take on the challenge of learning English by trusting their capacity and skills and developing good habits to see their progress. Self-directed learning in management indicates that Grade 10 language learners still need to be responsive in dealing with what they believe can best improve their English language.

Moreover, the learners' level of academic performance in English subjects is interpreted as outstanding. This finding would imply that the learners excelled academically, displayed proficiency in language-based tasks, and are still learning more strategies to improve their abilities.

A significant relationship between the learners' academic performance, self-efficacy, and self-directed English learning in terms of outside learning and ability was revealed from this finding. Since the study empirically established that a correlation exists between self-efficacy and academic performance. Thus, Grade 10 students must believe they can master a skill, subject, or activity without help. They also need to improve on their responsibility and initiative in diagnosing learning needs, creating learning plans, identifying human and material learning resources, choosing and implementing effective learning strategies, and assessing their learning achievements, with or without help.

Furthermore, the variables that, singly or in combination, best predict learners' academic performance are ability in self-directed English learning and self-efficacy. These confirm that the variables are essential to achieving academic performance among language learners. This finding means that these attributes greatly influence learners' academic performance. Hence, these must be given significant importance to enhance learners' language skills and abilities for better performance in the classroom and outside of English learning. Therefore, the ability to self-direct English learning and the self-efficacy beliefs of Grade 10 language learners are the best predictors of academic performance.

The conclusions and findings of this study summarized some essential ideas to be carried out for further use. The following are the recommendations:

The Department of Education may include topics in academic meetings that emphasize the relationship between language learning motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed English learning and academic accomplishment. School administrators may develop programs that continuously support learners' language learning motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed English learning, easing their doubts about their ability to attain academic goals. At the forefront of instruction, teachers could be mindful of the possibilities and provide adequate explanations for why learners hesitate in seemingly tricky academic work. In their training, they may highlight the interrelationship of language learning motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, self-directed learning, and academic performance. Any change in one will affect the others.

Language learning motivation, attitude, and management may also affect self-directed English learning, which was not observed to affect academic accomplishment in the current study. More study on self-efficacy in language learning, ability-based self-directed learning, and beyond classroom learning is needed. Since the study was limited to grade 10 high school learners, future researchers may want to look into these dimensions in senior high school learners and graduate school learners, along with pertinent demographic variables.

Moreover, these results may be utilized in designing practical academic development workshops and training for English learners that promote constructive motivational outcomes to enhance learners' effectiveness, efficiency, and timeliness. Training design may be done on the variables that best predict learners' academic performance in terms of ability in self-directed learning and self-efficacy of Grade 10 language learners.

Finally, studies on the academic performance of Grade 10 language learners and how motivation, attitude, self-efficacy, and self-directed English language learning affect it are possible.

References

- Adav, S., & Arora, A. (2021). Opinion of students on online education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies*.
- Agarwal, J., & Malhotra, N. K. (2005). An integrated model of attitude and affect: Theoretical foundation and an empirical investigation. *Journal of Business Research*.
- Agum, A. N. C., Naidas, M. S., Dorado, L. B., Bhattraï, J. L. T., & Lagajino, E. L. V. (2021). Filipino College Students' Perspectives on the Challenges, Coping Strategies, and Benefits of Self-Directed Language Learning in the New Normal. *Human Behavior, Development and Society*.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1975). A Bayesian analysis of attribution processes. *Psychological Bulletin*.
- Alieto, E., & Rillo, R. M. (2018). Language attitudes of English language teachers (ELTs) towards Philippine English.
- Alipio, M. (2020). Academic success as estimated by locus of control and motivation.
- Alipour, M., Salim, H., Stewart, R. A., & Sahin, O. (2020). Predictors, taxonomy of predictors, and correlations of predictors with the decision behaviour of residential solar photovoltaics adoption: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*.
- Al Samadani, H. A., & Ibnian, S. (2015). The relationship between Saudi EFL students' attitudes towards learning English and their academic achievement. *International Journal of Education and Social Science*.
- Altiner, C. (2018). Preparatory School Students' English Language Learning Motivation: A Sample from Turkey. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*.
- Alyami, M., Al-Sharef, A., Al-Aseri, M., & Henning, M. (2021). Mammography self-efficacy scale and breast cancer fear scale: Psychometric properties of the Arabic versions among Saudi women. *Cancer Nursing*.
- An, Y., & Zheng, Z. (2021). Conflicted immediacy provision. Available at SSRN 2868280.
- Ankiewicz, P. (2019). Perceptions and attitudes of pupils towards technology: In search of a rigorous theoretical framework. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*.
- Arda, S., & Doyran, F. (2017). Analysis of young learners' and teenagers' attitudes to English Language Learning. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*.
- Asfar, N., & Zainuddin, Z. (2015). Secondary students' perceptions of information, communication, and technology (ICT) use in promoting self-directed learning in Malaysia. *The Online Journal of Distance Education and E-Learning*.
- Aşkın, İ. (2015). Self-Directed Learning Skills Scale: Üniversite öğrencilerinin öz-yönetimli öğrenme becerilerinin incelenmesi.

- Autio, E. (2019). Innovation ecosystems. Available at SSRN 3476925.
- Awang, M. M., Jindal-Snape, D., & Barber, T. (2013). A documentary analysis of the Government's circulars on positive behavior enhancement strategies. *Asian Social Science*, 9(5), 203.
- Ayyildiz, Y., & Tarhan, L. (2015). Development of the self-directed learning skills scale. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*.
- Ball, J. W., Bice, M. R., & Maljak, K. A. (2017). Exploring the Relationship between Self-Determination Theory, Adults' Barriers to Exercise, and Physical Activity. *Health Educator*.
- Bandura, A. (1988). Organisational applications of social cognitive theory. *Australian Journal of Management*.
- Bandura, A., & Walters, R. H. (1977). *Social learning theory* (Vol. 1). Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
- Bråten, I., Johansen, R. P., & Strømsø, H. I. (2017). Effects of different ways of introducing a reading task on intrinsic motivation and comprehension. *Journal of Research in Reading*.
- Brem, A., Puente-Diaz, R., & Agogué, M. (2016). Creativity and innovation: State of the art and future perspectives for research. *International Journal of Innovation Management*.
- Burda, Y., Edwards, H., Pathak, D., Storkey, A., Darrell, T., & Efros, A. A. (2018). Large-scale study of curiosity-driven learning.
- Cabigon, M. (2015). State of English in the Philippines: Should we be concerned. *British Council Philippines*.
- Caldarella, P., Larsen, R. A., Williams, L., Wills, H. P., & Wehby, J. H. (2021). "Stop doing that!": Effects of teacher reprimands on student disruptive behavior and engagement. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*.
- Cazan, A. M., & Schiopca, B. A. (2014). Self-directed learning, personality traits, and academic achievement. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 127, 640–644.
- Chakraborty, P., et al. (2021). Depression, anxiety, and associated factors among Chinese adolescents during the COVID-19 outbreak: A comparison of two cross-sectional studies. *Translational Psychiatry*.
- Chakkaravarthy, K., et al. (2020). Determinants of readiness towards self-directed learning among nurses and midwives: Results from a national survey. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 47, 102824.
- Cherry, K. (2016). What is intrinsic motivation. *About.com Psychology*.
- Chua, K. E., & Karpudewan, M. (2017, December). The role of motivation and perceptions about science laboratory environment on lower secondary students' attitude towards science. *Asia-Pacific Forum on Science Learning and Teaching*, 18(2), 1–16. Hong Kong Institute of Education.
- Chrysidis, S., Turner, M. J., & Wood, A. G. (2020). The effects of REBT on irrational beliefs, self-determined motivation, and self-efficacy in American Football. *Journal of Sports Sciences*.
- Çiftci, F., Şen, E., Demir, N., Çiftci, O., Erol, S., & Kayacan, O. (2018). Beliefs, attitudes, and activities of healthcare personnel about influenza and pneumococcal vaccines. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*.
- Claiborne, L., Morrell, J., Bandy, J., Bruff, D., Smith, G., & Fedesco, H. (2014). *Teaching outside the classroom*. Center for Teaching at Vanderbilt University.
- Coşkun, G., & TAŞGIN, A. (2018). An investigation of anxiety and attitudes of university students towards English courses. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*.
- Crandall, P. G., O'Bryan, C. A., Killian, S. A., Beck, D. E., Jarvis, N., & Clausen, E. (2015). A comparison of the degree of student satisfaction using a simulation or a traditional wet lab to teach physical properties of ice. *Journal of Food Science Education*.
- Csizér, K. (2019). The L2 motivational self-system. In *The Palgrave Handbook of Motivation for Language Learning*.
- Curry, N., Mynard, J., Noguchi, J., & Watkins, S. (2017). Evaluating a self-directed language learning course in a Japanese university. *International Journal of Self-Directed Learning*.
- Daguay-James, H., & Bulusan, F. (2020). Metacognitive strategies on reading English texts of ESL freshmen: A sequential explanatory mixed design. *TESOL International Journal*.
- Dawson, S., Macfadyen, L., Risko, E. F., Foulsham, T., & Kingstone, A. (2012). Using technology to encourage self-directed learning: The collaborative lecture annotation system. In *ASCILITE 2012 – Annual Conference of the Australian Society for Computers in Tertiary Education* (pp. 246–255).
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). Cognitive evaluation theory. In *Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in Human Behavior*.

Springer, Boston, MA.

DeFleur, M. L., & Westie, F. R. (1963). Attitude as a scientific concept. *Social Forces*.

Demir, Ö., & Yurdugül, H. (2015). The exploration of models regarding e-learning readiness: Reference model suggestions. *International Journal of Progressive Education*.

Derakhshan, A. (2021). The predictability of Turkman students' academic engagement through Persian language teachers' nonverbal immediacy and credibility.

Devkota, R., Khan, G. M., Alam, K., Sapkota, B., & Devkota, D. (2017). Impacts of counseling on knowledge, attitude, and practice of medication use during pregnancy. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*.

Dixson, M. D., Greenwell, M. R., Rogers-Stacy, C., Weister, T., & Lauer, S. (2017). Nonverbal immediacy behaviors and online student engagement: Bringing past instructional research into the present virtual classroom. *Communication Education*.

Dogan, U. (2015). Student engagement, academic self-efficacy, and academic motivation as predictors of academic performance. *The Anthropologist*.

Dookhan, K. O. (2021). Relationship between students' self-directed learning and motivation for online learning at undergraduate university level in Mauritius.

Dorji, T., Tshering, T., & Wangdi, K. (2020). Assessment of knowledge, attitude, and practice on tuberculosis among teacher trainees of Samtse College of Education, Bhutan. *PLOS One*.

Downs, A. (2017). From theory to practice: The promise of primary care in New Zealand (p. 74). Fulbright New Zealand.

Dweck, C. S., & Master, A. (2009). Self-theories and motivation: Students' beliefs about intelligence. In *Handbook of Motivation at School*. Routledge.

Farid, A., & Lamb, M. (2020). English for Da'wah? L2 motivation in Indonesian pesantren schools. *System*.

Frerk, C., Mitchell, V. S., McNarry, A. F., Mendonca, C., Bhagrath, R., Patel, A., ... & Ahmad, I. (2015). Difficult Airway Society 2015 guidelines for management of unanticipated difficult intubation in adults. *BJA: British Journal of Anaesthesia*.

Fryer, M., & Roger, P. (2018). Transformations in the L2 self: Changing motivation in a study abroad context. *System*.

Gao, A., & Jiang, J. (2019). Perceived empowering leadership, harmonious passion, and employee voice: The moderating role of job autonomy. *Frontiers in Psychology*.

Gao, Y. (2021). Toward the role of language teacher confirmation and stroke in EFL/ESL students' motivation and academic engagement: A theoretical review. *Frontiers in Psychology*.

Garrison, D. R. (1997). Self-directed learning: Toward a comprehensive model. *Adult Education Quarterly*.

Gustilo, L., & Dimaculangan, N. (2018). Attitudes of Filipino English teachers toward 21st century Philippine English writing. *Advanced Science Letters*.

Hacieminoglu, E. (2016). Elementary School Students' Attitude toward Science and Related Variables. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*.

Haidari, S. M., Yelken, T. Y., & Cenk, A. K. A. Y. (2019). Technology-enhanced self-directed language learning behaviors of EFL student teachers. *Contemporary Educational Technology*.

Hajloo, N. (2014). Relationships between self-efficacy, self-esteem and procrastination in undergraduate psychology students. *Iranian Journal of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences*, 8(3), 42.

Halil, E. K. Ş. İ., Demirci, İ., Albayrak, İ., & Füsün, E. K. Ş. İ. (2022). The predictive roles of character strengths and personality traits on flourishing. *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*.

Hashiguchi, N., Sengoku, S., Kubota, Y., Kitahara, S., Lim, Y., & Kodama, K. (2021). Age-dependent influence of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations on construction worker performance. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*.

Hass, R. W., Katz-Buonincontro, J., & Reiter-Palmon, R. (2016). Disentangling creative mindsets from creative self-efficacy and creative identity: Do people hold fixed and growth theories of creativity? *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*.

Hong, J. C., Ye, J. H., & Fan, J. Y. (2019). STEM in Fashion Design: The roles of creative self-efficacy and epistemic curiosity in creative performance. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*.

Honick, T., & Broadbent, J. (2016). The influence of academic self-efficacy on academic performance: A systematic review.

Educational Research Review.

Howard, J. L., Bureau, J., Guay, F., Chong, J. X., & Ryan, R. M. (2021). Student motivation and associated outcomes: A meta-analysis from self-determination theory. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*.

Jaleel, S., & OM, A. (2017). A study on the relationship between self-directed learning and achievement in information technology of students at secondary level. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 5(10), 1849-1852.

Khalid, M., Bashir, S., & Amin, H. (2020). Relationship between Self-Directed Learning (SDL) and Academic Achievement of University Students: A Case of Online Distance Learning and Traditional Universities. *Bulletin of Education and Research*.

Khan, A. A., Siddiqui, A. Z., Mohsin, S. F., Al Momani, M. M., & Mirza, E. H. (2017). Impact of network-aided platforms as educational tools on academic performance and attitude of pharmacology students. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*.

Ko, E., & Kim, H. Y. (2017). Effects of simulation-based education combined team-based learning on self-directed learning, communication skills, nursing performance confidence and team efficacy in nursing students. *Journal of Korean Academy of Fundamentals of Nursing*.

Kuvaas, B., Buch, R., & Dysvik, A. (2020). Individual variable pay for performance, controlling effects, and intrinsic motivation. *Motivation and Emotion*.

LaBelle, S., & Johnson, Z. D. (2020). The relationship of student-to-student confirmation and student engagement. *Communication Research Reports*.

Larsen, C., Walsh, C., Almond, N., & Myers, C. (2017). The “real value” of field trips in the early weeks of higher education: the student perspective. *Educational Studies*.

Lazar, A., & Nguyen, D. H. (2017, May). Successful Leisure in Independent Living Communities: Understanding Older Adults' Motivations to Engage in Leisure Activities. In *Proceedings of the 2017 chi conference on human factors in computing systems*.

Legault, L. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. *Encyclopedia of personality and individual differences*.

Li, J., Yang, D., & Hu, Z. (2021). Wuhan College Students' Self-Directed Learning and Academic Performance: Chain-Mediating Roles of Optimism and Mental Health. *Frontiers in Psychology*.

Liu, W. (2021). Does teacher immediacy affect students? A systematic review of the association between teacher verbal and non-verbal immediacy and student motivation. *Frontiers in Psychology*.

Madrugno, M. R., Martin, I. P., & Plata, S. M. (2016). English language education in the Philippines: Policies, problems, and prospects. In *English language education policy in Asia* Springer, Cham.

Magulod, G. C. (2017). Creativity styles and emotional intelligence of Filipino student teachers: A search for congruity. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*.

Magulod Jr, G. C. (2017). Educational philosophies adhered by Filipino preservice teachers: Basis for proposing initiatives for 21st century teacher education preparation program. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*.

Malison, K., & Thammakoranonta, N. (2018). An exploratory study of self-directed learning: The differences between IT and non-IT employees in Thailand. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*.

Marquez-Leccio, B. J. (2016). Self-directed learning: teacher and learner. *International Education & Research Journal [IERJ]*.

Moradi, H. (2017). The impact of M-learning on second language learning process among university students. *Modern Journal of Language Teaching Methods*.

Moradi, H. (2018). Self-directed learning in language teaching-learning processes. *Modern Journal of Language Teaching Methods (MJLTM)*.

Namazandost, E., & Çakmak, F. (2020). An account of EFL learners' self-efficacy and gender in the Flipped Classroom Model. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(5), 4041-4055.

Nasir, M., & Iqbal, S. (2019). Academic Self Efficacy as a Predictor of Academic Achievement of Students in Pre Service Teacher Training Programs. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 41(1), 33-42.

Nasirudeen, A. M. A., & Xiao, S. (2020). English language skills and academic performance: A comparison between Asian international and domestic nursing students in Singapore. *International Journal of Nursing*, 7(1), 30-38.

Niemi, L., & Young, L. (2016). When and why we see victims as responsible: The impact of ideology on attitudes toward victims. *Personality and social psychology bulletin*.

- Nikolov, M. (1999). 'Why do you learn English? 'Because the teacher is short.' A study of Hungarian children's foreign language learning motivation. *Language Teaching Research*.
- Nurhasanah, S., & Sobandi, A. (2016). Learning Interest as a Determinant of Student Learning Outcomes. *JOURNAL OF Office Management Education*.
- Nyamubi, G. J. (2016). Students' Attitudes and English Language Performance in Secondary Schools in Tanzania. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*.
- Ode, D. (2018). Effect of Extrinsic Motivation on Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Social Studies. *International Journal of Education (IJE)*.
- Ojo, B. Y., & Yusof, R. N. R. (2019). Edu-Tourism Destination Selection Process in an Emerging Economy. *Journal of Tourism Management Research*.
- Orhan Özen, S. (2017). The effect of motivation on student achievement. In *The factors effecting student achievement* (pp. 35-56). Springer, Cham.
- Oudeyer, P. Y., Gottlieb, J., & Lopes, M. (2016). Intrinsic motivation, curiosity, and learning: Theory and applications in educational technologies. *Progress in brain research*.
- Perloff, R. M. (2016). Attitudes: Definition and structure. In *The Dynamics of Persuasion* Routledge.
- Philp, J., & Duchesne, S. (2016). Exploring engagement in tasks in the language classroom. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*.
- Prestridge, S. (2012). The beliefs behind the teacher that influences their ICT practices. *Computers & education*, 58(1), 449-458.
- Pretz, J. E., & Kaufman, J. C. (2017). Do traditional admissions criteria reflect applicant creativity? *The Journal of Creative Behavior*.
- Rampai, N. (2015). Model of Knowledge Management via Social Media to Enhance Graduated Student's Self-Directed Learning Skill. *International journal of information and education Technology*.
- Rashid, T., & Asghar, H. M. (2016). Technology use, self-directed learning, student engagement and academic performance: Examining the interrelations. *Computers in Human Behavior*.
- Reeve, J., & Lee, W. (2019). A neuroscientific perspective on basic psychological needs. *Journal of personality*.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). *Self-determination theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness*. Guilford Publications.
- Saeid, N., & Eslaminejad, T. (2017). Relationship between Student's Self-Directed-Learning Readiness and Academic Self-Efficacy and Achievement Motivation in Students. *International Education Studies*.
- Salanga, M. G. C., & Bernardo, A. B. (2016). Filipino students' reasons for not being motivated in school: Insights into their implicit beliefs about motivation and learning. In *The Psychology of Asian Learners* (pp. 85-98). Springer, Singapore.
- Salayo, J., & Amarles, A. M. (2020). Relationship between Anxiety in Second Language Learning and Motivation Orientation: The Case of Young Filipino Learners. *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies*.
- Schneider, M., & Preckel, F. (2017). Variables associated with achievement in higher education: A systematic review of meta-analyses. *Psychological bulletin*, 143(6), 565.
- Schunk, D. H., & DiBenedetto, M. K. (2020). Motivation and social cognitive theory. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*.
- Selva, J. (2021). Albert Ellis' ABC Model in the Cognitive Behavioral Therapy Spotlight. *Positive Psychology*.
- Shen, T., & Croucher, S. M. (2018). A cross-cultural analysis of teacher confirmation and student motivation in China, Korea, and Japan. *J. Intercult. Commun.*
- Snow, D., Bundy, A., Tranter, P., Wyver, S., Naughton, G., Ragen, J., & Engelen, L. (2019). Girls' perspectives on the ideal school playground experience: An exploratory study of four Australian primary schools. *Children's geographies*.
- Song, D., & Kim, P. (2015). Inquiry-based mobilized math classroom with Stanford mobile inquiry-based learning environment (SMILE). *Mobile learning and STEM: Case studies in practice*.
- Strombach, T., Strang, S., Park, S. Q., & Kenning, P. (2016). Common and distinctive approaches to motivation in different disciplines. *Progress in brain research*.
- Svenningsson, J., Höst, G., Hultén, M., & Hallström, J. (2021). Students' attitudes toward technology: Exploring the relationship among affective, cognitive and behavioral components of the attitude construct. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*.

- Taguchi, N. (2018). Description and explanation of pragmatic development: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods research. System.
- Talsma, K., Schüz, B., Schwarzer, R., & Norris, K. (2018). I believe, therefore I achieve (and vice versa): A meta-analytic cross-lagged panel analysis of self-efficacy and academic performance. *Learning and Individual Differences*.
- Tanni, Z. A. I. (2015). Attitudes toward English among Al-Quds Open University Students in Tulkarm Branch. *World Journal of Education*.
- Tekkol, İ. A., & Demirel, M. (2018). An investigation of self-directed learning skills of undergraduate students. *Frontiers in psychology*.
- Tokoz-Goktepe, F. (2014). Speaking problems of 9th grade high school Turkish learners of L2 English and possible reasons for those problems: Exploring the teachers and students' perspectives. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 116, 1875-1879.
- Üstün, B., & Aksu Ataç, B. (2022). Attitudes of Foreign Language Teaching Students towards Online Learning. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching*.
- Verešová, M., & Mala, D. (2016). Attitude toward school and learning and academic achievement of adolescents. In 7th International Conference on Education and Educational Psychology, Published by Future Academy.
- Walberg, H. J. (1982). Educational productivity: Theory, evidence, and prospects. *Australian Journal of Education*.
- Wallace, M. P., & Leong, E. I. L. (2020). Exploring language learning motivation among primary EFL learners. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*.
- Xie, B., Nelson, G. L., Akkaraju, H., Kwok, W., & Ko, A. J. (2020, August). The effect of informing agency in Self-Directed online learning environments. In *Proceedings of the Seventh ACM Conference on Learning@ Scale*.
- Yazon, A. D. (2015). Self-esteem, self-efficacy and academic performance of the college of teacher education students at the Laguna State Polytechnic University. *Proceeding of the 3rd Global Summit on Education GSE*, 436-453.
- Yilmaz, R. (2017). Exploring the role of e-learning readiness on student satisfaction and motivation in flipped classroom. *Computers in Human Behavior*.
- Zhou, L., & Li, C. (2020). Can student self-directed learning improve their academic performance? Experimental evidence from the instruction of protocol-guided learning in China's elementary and middle schools. *Experimental Evidence from the Instruction of Protocol-Guided Learning in China's Elementary and Middle Schools*.

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